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Profiling scuba divers' behaviour
and marketing preferences to
Portofino
MPA

Profiling scuba divers' behaviour and marketing preferences to **Portofino** MPA

This research forms part of the Green Bubbles RISE Project

Green Bubbles

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TOURISM RESEARCH IN ECONOMIC ENVIRONS AND SOCIETY

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1. INTRODUCTION

Marine tourism is one of the tourism industry's fastest expanding markets across the world and includes recreational activities that take place in a marine environment (MPA). Over the years, marine tourism has evolved into a multi-dimensional market with a wide variety of activities to offer, such as surfing, scuba diving, snorkelling, kayaking, deep sea fishing and boating. The Portofino Marine Protected Area extends around the promontory of the same name among the Municipalities of Camogli, Portofino and Santa Margherita Ligure. The coast appears in all its charm: fascinating views and small inlets covered with the vegetation stroking the sea. Along the southern side, there are underwater cliffs reaching very deep levels where micro-habitats – which is rare for the Mediterranean area – originates.

Green Bubbles is dedicated to recreational scuba diving, an activity engaging millions of people worldwide – yet poorly studied within the European context. Green Bubbles aims to maximise the benefits associated with diving while minimising its negative impacts, thereby achieving the environmental, economic and social sustainability of the system with a specific focus on the European diving industry.

To analyse the scuba diving market in Marine Protected Areas, researchers from TREES (as part of the Green Bubbles consortium) conducted a survey to determine the travel behaviour and loyalty levels of divers. The results of these findings are discussed in this report.

2. AIM OF THE RESEARCH

This research had the following primary aims:

- To determine the profile of scuba divers to Portofino;
- To determine the social media preferences of scuba divers;
- To determine the travel motivations for diving;
- To determine the loyalty levels of scuba divers to Portofino.

3. METHOD OF STUDY

To achieve these aims, the following approach was implemented: Firstly, a questionnaire was developed and administered by researchers from TREES at the North-West University in collaboration with the dive operators in Portofino. Secondly, it was distributed in the following sampling areas, namely Santa Margherita, Rapallo and Recco. Respondents were approached and the aims of the study were explained, after which the questionnaires were handed to them for completion after they provided their consent. Participation was, therefore, voluntary and the questionnaire was available in English and Italian. Quantitative research was therefore implemented for this research and based on convenience sampling, 291 respondents formed part of the study from June to August 2016. It was completed on-site after which all questionnaires were captured on Microsoft Excel and analysed through SPSS (Version 24).

The research was done at the following dive operators in Santa Margherita and surrounding environments:

- DWS (Luca, Pino, Marco, Federico)
- Evolution Dive (Andrea, Johnny)
- Tortuga (Arnaldo, Eleanora, Giullia)
- Dive Passion (Stefano, Luca)
- Portofino Dive (Bruno)
- European Dive (Filippo)
- Style Diving (Marco);
- Bubble Lounge (Franco).

4. RESULTS

Section A: Socio-demographic profile of visitors

This section presents the socio-demographic profile of scuba divers.

4.1 GENDER

This figure illustrates that seventy-four percent (74%) of participants were male and 26% of the participants were female.

4.2 AGE

It is clear that the highest percentage (40%) of participants were between the ages of 35 and 49 years, followed by those between the ages of 50 and 64 years (32%) and 16% were between the ages of 25 and 34 years. The younger group of participants of 19 years and younger accounted for 5% and those who were 20 to 24 years, 5%. The smallest group of participants (2%) were participants who were 65 years and older. The average age of respondents was 43 years of age.

4.3 EDUCATION

The largest percentage of participants (38%) indicated that they had obtained a diploma, followed by 34% who obtained a degree from a tertiary institution. Seventeen percent of the participants have matric, 9% have a post-graduate degree, and a small percentage (2%) has other qualifications, which were not specified.

4.4 MARITAL STATUS

According to the figure, the largest percentage of participants (49%) was single, followed by those participants who were married (42%), and those who were divorced (6%). There is clearly a preference among single persons for scuba diving.

DID YOU KNOW?
Most respondents were
SINGLE

4.5 OCCUPATION

The participants were asked to indicate their current occupation. This figure illustrates the top five occupations of the participants. The largest percentage of participants (20%) is in a clerical position, followed by 12% who considered themselves office workers and 11% who are students. Six percent of the participants indicated that they are employed, and 4% are retired.

4.6 COUNTRY OF RESIDENCE

The majority of participants (92%) who dive at Portofino during June are from Italy, while 8% travelled from countries such as Argentina, Austria, Canada, China, France, Germany, Norway, Spain, Switzerland and the USA.

Respondents were, therefore, 43-year-old single males with a diploma or a degree in clerical positions living in Italy. Even though it is high season during June, the presence of other nationalities is almost non-existing (8%), which creates various opportunities for MPA of Portofino as a diving site.

Section B: Travel behaviour of divers to Portofino

Section B presents the travel behaviour of divers.

4.7 NUMBER OF NIGHTS STAYING

As indicated in the figure below, the majority of participants (80%) spend five or fewer nights in the area. Six percent stayed between six and 10 nights, followed by the groups of participants (4%) who stayed between 11 and 15 nights

and 3% who stayed between 16 and 20 nights. Participants spend an average of five nights at the destination. There is enormous potential to increase visitors' length of stay to enjoy other attractions in the area as well.

Number of nights	Percentage %
<5 nights	80%
6-10 nights	6%
11-15 nights	4%
16-20 nights	3%
21-25 nights	1%
26-30 nights	4%
31-35 nights	0.1%
36-40 nights	0.4%
41> nights	1%

Average nights stayed: 5 nights

DID YOU KNOW?
 Respondents stayed for an average of
5 NIGHTS

4.8 NUMBER OF PEOPLE PAID FOR

Forty-seven percent (47%) of the participants paid for one person, followed by 25% who were responsible for two people. Twelve percent indicated that they did not pay for anyone. Furthermore, 9% paid for three people, 4% paid for four people and 3% were responsible for paying for five people. The average number of people that participants paid for was two people.

Number paid for	Percentage %
0 people	12%
1 person	47%
2 people	25%
3 people	9%
4 people	4%
5 people	3%

Average number paid for: 2

Respondents were financially
 responsible for
2 PEOPLE

4.9 SPENDING

As seen in the figure, the average participant spends approximately €241 on various activities during their trip. In total the largest amount of money was spent on accommodation (€14063), followed by dives (€13803), food and beverages (€12165). In total, the sample population had spent €69 970 on various activities during their trip in the Ligure region.

Activity	Average spend	Total spend
Scuba dives (i.e. only the dive, plus boat lift)	€48	€13 803
Dive course and/or additional training	€22	€6 399
Accommodation	€48	€14 063
Transportation (air and ground travel)	€24	€6 879
Shopping	€12	€3 460
Food and beverages	€42	€12 165
Diving insurance/ Renewal of dive credentials	€6	€1 880
Buying new scuba diving equipment/ gear	€15	€4 328
Hiring scuba diving equipment/ gear	€13	€3 716
Other activities (e.g. boat trips)	€3	€730
Other expenses not listed	€9	€2 547
Total	€241	€69 970

4.10 MAIN REASONS FOR DIVING AT PORTOFINO

Respondents were asked to indicate to what extent they agree with selected reasons for diving at Portofino. These statements were shown on a 5 point Likert scale (where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree).

Main reasons for diving at Portofino:	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Mean value	Std. deviation
To learn more about specific marine species	6%	10%	48%	30%	6%	3.19	0.91
To experience the exotic atmosphere of Portofino	4%	11%	35%	40%	10%	3.41	0.95
To experience peace and tranquillity	3%	4%	25%	41%	26%	3.83	0.95
The marine life is well protected in Portofino	1%	3%	10%	49%	36%	4.17	0.80
I never know what to expect from each dive	1%	3%	25%	47%	23%	3.88	0.84
To rest and relax	2%	6%	29%	41%	22%	3.74	0.94
Portofino offers a unique diving experience	1%	5%	33%	43%	18%	3.72	0.83
It was on my 'bucket list' to dive here	5%	10%	47%	27%	10%	3.43	2.70
Good weather and climate	1%	3%	34%	48%	14%	3.73	0.77
Portofino is a world-class diving site	1%	5%	35%	41%	16%	3.65	0.87
To escape from routine	4%	5%	33%	38%	19%	3.64	0.98
To enhance my knowledge as a diver	3%	4%	22%	46%	25%	3.85	0.93

Main reasons for diving at Portofino:	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Mean value	Std. deviation
Dive operators adhere to safety regulations	1%	1%	20%	44%	33%	4.08	0.82
To socialise with other divers	2%	7%	30%	44%	16%	3.66	0.91
Portofino offers good shopping opportunities	17%	23%	40%	14%	6%	2.70	1.09
To find relief from everyday tension	4%	4%	35%	41%	15%	3.59	0.93
To explore a new destination	4%	8%	44%	35%	9%	3.36	0.91
Portofino has quality beaches	11%	21%	41%	22%	5%	2.90	1.03
To dive in a marine protected area	2%	1%	16%	45%	36%	4.12	0.85
Portofino offers beautiful scenic beauty	1%	1%	18%	54%	26%	4.04	0.76
To meet new people	3%	8%	40%	37%	11%	3.44	0.92
To develop my diving skills and abilities	2%	2%	23%	49%	23%	3.90	0.85
To participate in a diving course	12%	14%	41%	24%	8%	3.03	1.10
To spend time with friends and family	4%	6%	31%	44%	13%	3.57	0.95
Diving here is value for money	6%	10%	35%	40%	8%	3.34	0.98
Portofino offers quality restaurants	3%	8%	49%	29%	10%	3.34	0.90
There are a variety of attractions to visit	3%	8%	49%	32%	8%	3.33	0.85
Diving sites are easily accessible	2%	1%	19%	56%	21%	3.91	0.81

The most important reasons respondents choose the MPA in Portofino as diving site are:

- The marine life is well protected in Portofino (4.17)
- They want to dive in a marine protected area (4.12)
- The dive operators adhere to safety regulations (4.08)
- Portofino offers beautiful scenic beauty (4.04)
- Diving sites are easily accessible (3.91)

The least important aspects were good shopping areas and good beaches.

4.11 RECOMMEND THIS AREA AS DIVING DESTINATION

Ninety-six percent (96%) of the participants indicated that they would definitely recommend the area as a diving destination to others. Three percent felt unsure, and 1% indicated that they would definitely not recommend this area as a diving destination to other.

These respondents, therefore, stay for less than five nights in Portofino, pay for one person during the trip, spend an average of €241 while visiting and would recommend this area to other divers. Their main reason for choosing the area as a dive destination is related to the well-protected marine life in Portofino (MPA).

Section C: Scuba-related behaviour of divers

This section provides an overview of the participant’s scuba diving behaviour patterns

4.12 FIRST VISIT TO PORTOFINO

It is clear that respondents were familiar with Portofino with only 26% indicating that it was their first visit to this area. Again, there is potential to increase the number of first-time visitors to this area and focus thereafter on the retention of these visitors.

DID YOU KNOW?
Most respondents had visited Portofino previously

4.13 NUMBER OF PREVIOUS VISITS

Number of previous visits	Percentage
<10	52%
11-20	16%
21-30	7%
31-40	1%
41-50	4%

51-100	14%
101-200	3%
201-300	2%
301-400	1%
401-500	0.5%
501>	3%

The largest percentage of participants (52%) indicated that they had visited the destination 10 times or less, followed by the group of participants (16%) that visited previously between 11 and 20 times. 14% indicated that they had visited the destination previously between 51 and 100 times and 7% between 21 and 30 times. Once the visitors have been to Portofino, there is an intention to return.

4.14 NUMBER OF YEARS DIVING

The table below illustrates the number of years that participants been diving. The largest percentage (38%) of participants indicated they have been diving for less than five years, followed by 21% that have been diving between six and 10 years. Thirteen percent of the participants have been diving between 11 and 15 years and 11% between 16 and 20 years. Ten percent indicated that they have been diving between 31 and 35 years. A small percentage (2%) indicated that they have been diving for 40 years and more. Although the highest percentage of respondents has been diving for less than five years, high loyalty levels to this activity are evident.

Number of years diving	Percentage
<5 years	38%
6-10 years	21%
11-15 years	13%
16-20 years	11%
21-25 years	5%
26-30 years	4%
31-35 years	10%
36-40 years	2%
40+ years	2%

DID YOU KNOW?
On average, respondents had
been diving for
12 YEARS

Average number of years diving: 12

4.15 NUMBER OF DIVES LOGGED

Participants were asked to estimate the number of dives they have logged since they started diving. The largest percentage (51%) indicated that they had logged approximately 100 dives or less, followed by the group of participants (20%) who indicated that they have logged between 101 and 300 dives. Ten percent of the participants logged approximately 1 000 dives and more, 6% logged between 301 and 500 dives, 5% between 701 and 900 and 4%

indicated that they have logged between 501 and 700 dives. The median number of dives logged is 11 dives. This clearly shows their love of diving.

4.16 NUMBER OF DIVES PER YEAR

The majority of participants (83%) dive approximately 50 times or less per year. Eleven percent of the participants dive between 51 and 100 times per year, followed by the group of participants (3%) who dive between 101 and 150 times per year.

4.17 LEVEL OF DIVING CERTIFICATION

The majority of participants were either instructors (53 respondents) or advanced open water divers (52 respondents). The number of open water divers was also a significant part of this sample namely 36 respondents. There are therefore a variety of divers utilising Portofino as a dive destination.

Diving certification	Frequency
Instructors	53
Dive masters	27
Deep diving	28
Open water	36
Advanced open water	52
Rescue diving	19
Decompression Diver	3
CMAS 1-4 stars	10
Other certifications	23

4.18 DISCIPLINES/TYPES OF RECREATIONAL DIVING

From the respondents who completed this question, 19% preferred cave diving and recreational diving (19%). Eighteen percent preferred different types of diving and 17% wreck diving.

Types of diving	Percentage
Free and natural	11%
All types of diving	18%
Cave diving	19%
Recreational diving	19%
Reef diving	5%
Technical diving	2%
Wall diving	10%
Wreck diving	17%

Section C: Media preferences of divers

In this section, respondents' preferences regarding social media usage were assessed. This can be used as a marketing medium by dive operators.

4.19 SOCIAL MEDIA

Respondents were asked to indicate to what extent they agree with a list of statements related to the use of social media. These statements were indicated on a 5 point Likert scale (where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree).

I would or do make use of social media such as Facebook to:	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Mean value
Book diving holidays/dives	10%	7%	33%	36%	14%	3.37
Enquire about a booking	9%	4%	14%	47%	26%	3.77
Review exclusive dive offers	8%	5%	21%	45%	21%	3.66
Obtain more information about the dive site	9%	3%	13%	45%	29%	3.82
Obtain contact information of a specific dive operator	7%	65	20%	46%	20%	3.67
Do research about a specific dive site	8%	6%	17%	45%	22%	3.66
Collect information about a specific dive site	8%	6%	17%	47%	22%	3.70
Benefit from a wide range of knowledge about dive sites	8%	4%	23%	45%	20%	3.65
Share my experiences diving at specific sites	7%	7%	30%	36%	19%	3.54
Compare dive destinations	7%	6%	29%	39%	18%	3.53
Write a review of a specific dive destination	9%	9%	29%	36%	16%	3.43
Interact with other divers or dive operators	7%	5%	29%	40%	17%	3.54
Ask for dive site advice	7%	5%	23%	46%	18%	3.62
Read the reviews written by others	6%	5%	21%	48%	20%	3.69
To obtain information about courses	8%	10%	29%	37%	14%	3.40
To post photos, videos etc. of specific diving experiences	9%	7%	25%	34%	23%	3.55

Respondents use social media to:

- Obtain more information about the dive site (3.82)
- Enquire about a booking (3.77)
- Collect information about a specific dive site (3.70)
- Read the reviews written by others (3.69)
- Obtain contact information of a specific dive operators (3.67)

Not one of the statements revealed a mean value of above 4, which indicates that social media is not the optimal marketing medium used to gather information regarding dive operators and their operations.

Section D: Loyalty levels of respondents

The high number of return visitors indicates their loyalty to Portofino as a diving destination and it is important to determine what influences their loyalty.

4.20 LOYALTY TO PORTOFINO AS DIVING SITE

Respondents were asked to indicate to what extent they agree with a list of loyalty factors to Portofino as a diving site. These statements were indicated on a five-point Likert scale (where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree).

Loyalty to Portofino as diving site	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Mean value
I would recommend others to visit Portofino as diving site	4%	0%	5%	42%	49%	4.33
I will visit Portofino in the future	3%	1%	4%	38%	53%	4.37
Portofino is now my first choice among diving destinations	5%	19%	42%	24%	9%	3.14
I will say positive things about this diving site	2%	1%	8%	46%	42%	4.26
I would recommend others to use this dive operator	3%	1%	9%	40%	46%	4.26
I will make use of this dive operator again in the future	3%	5%	30%	33%	29%	3.81
This dive operator is now my first choice among dive operators	3%	2%	35%	25%	35%	3.88
I will say positive things about this dive operator	3%	1%	10%	43%	43%	4.23
The information offered by the dive operator/s is honest	2%	1%	8%	49%	39%	4.23
In general the dive operator/s fulfils their commitments	3%	1%	10%	40%	45%	4.24
The dive operator is concerned about their divers' needs	2%	0%	11%	42%	44%	4.25
The dive operator has the resources & experience to do a good job	3%	0%	8%	43%	45%	4.51
I feel safe with the dive operator	3%	0%	11%	42%	44%	4.24
My choice to dive at Portofino was a wise one	3%	1%	11%	41%	44%	4.23
I enjoyed my dive/s	2%	1%	10%	44%	42%	4.24
The diving experience made me happy	3%	1%	13%	44%	40%	4.17
The dive/s was an unique experience	1%	1%	30%	38%	29%	3.91
Diving at Portofino fulfilled my expectations	2%	1%	20%	45%	31%	4.00
All contact made with the dive operators and staff was satisfactory	3%	1%	7%	45%	44%	4.27
I am in general satisfied with my diving experience	3%	1%	6%	40%	49%	4.33

Respondents were loyal to Portofino:

- because the dive operators have the resources and experience to do a good job (4.51)
- and will visit Portofino in the future (4.37)
- and would recommend others to visit Portofino as diving site (4.33)
- and are in general satisfied with his/her diving experience (4.33)
- since all contact made with the dive operators and staff was satisfactory (4.27)

- and would recommend others to use this dive operator (4.26)
- and will make use of this dive operator again in the future (4.26)

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The following conclusions and recommendations can be drawn from this report:

5.1 CONCLUSIONS REGARDING THE STUDY

- The majority of the respondents are male, with an average age of 43 years, hold either a diploma or a degree, are single or married, working in a clerical position and stay in Italy.
- When visiting Portofino they stay for less than five nights, pay for one person, spend on average €241 during their trip and they would recommend this destination to others.
- It is clear that respondents choose this dive destination due to the well-protected marine life in Portofino, their motivation to dive in such a site, the notion that the operators adhere to safety regulations, that Portofino has beautiful scenery and that their diving sites are accessible.
- This diving destination is very popular with 74% indicating that they visited this site before. These respondents have visited Portofino ten times or less. There were, however, 26% new visitors to the area.
- Most of the respondents have been diving for five years or less, with the majority logging less than 50 dives per year. Respondents have logged on average 418 dives since they started diving.
- It can be concluded that the divers are well educated in terms of diving certification where most of the divers were instructors or advance open water divers. These respondents enjoy all types of diving, but some indicated a preference for recreational diving, cave diving and wreck diving.
- With specific reference to social media, it was found that respondents use this medium to obtain information about the diving site and to enquire about a booking.
- The loyalty of the respondents to this destination lies in the hands of the operators, since divers return due to the dive operators having the necessary resources and experience to do a good job.
- It is good to note that these respondents will return to Portofino in the future and that they will recommend it to other divers.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS REGARDING THE STUDY

- That dive operators keep up the good work they are doing and that they focus on innovation to satisfy the return visitor to Portofino. Sustaining the current personal relationships with the divers, providing individual attention and showing an interest in their diving highlights and experiences are important.
- That a coordinated marketing effort between the dive operators is developed to create higher levels of awareness about this diving site internationally. An integrated marketing plan should be developed so that all dive operators can benefit from this plan.
- The social media sites are regularly updated and followed to reply to comments, react to posts, upload photos and manage bookings of dives.
- Group package deals (including dives, accommodation and meals) can be developed to attract larger groups, which will translate into an increase in group size.

- The protection of the MPA is of the utmost importance as it is the key pin to the diving industry in Portofino. More money from government needs to be allocated to conservation of the MPA, as it improves tourism to dive sites, which, in turn, generate income to the region. The MPA should actively market diving as one of their key activities to support the diving industry in this area.
- Diver operators might consider developing a conservation card (loyalty) to offer divers an incentive after a specific number of dives.